

Urban Relief

Best practices, methods and guidelines for inclusive community labs

D2.3

Document Factsheet

Grant agreement	101086638
Call identifier	Horizon-CL6-2022-Governance-01-08
Project title	Urban ReLeaf: Citizen-powered data ecosystems for inclusive and green urban transitions
Project start date	01/01/2023
Duration	48 months
Instrument	Horizon Europe
Type of action	Innovation action
Deliverable number	D2.3
Deliverable name	Best practices, methods and guidelines for inclusive community labs
Work package	WP2: Stakeholder dialogue and inclusive citizen participation
Task	T2.3: Pop-up community and culture labs
Deliverable lead	UNIVDUN
Deliverable type	Report
Due date	31/12/2025
Review completed	18/12/2025
Submission date	22/12/2025
Document version	1.0

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Acknowledgement

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Reference

Please cite this work as:

Woods, M (2025). Best practices, methods and guidelines for inclusive community labs. D2.3 for the Horizon Europe and Innovate UK co-funded project Urban ReLeaf under grant agreement ID: 101086638, 10061290 and 10041792. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18014907

Deliverable name	Best practices, methods and guidelines for inclusive community labs
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Short description	This deliverable documents the design, implementation and interim application of Community and Culture Pop-Up Labs developed under Task 2.3 of the Urban ReLeaf project. It presents a structured yet adaptable creative commissioning framework that supports cities in translating environmental data into accessible cultural and community-based experiences. Drawing on early implementation across 6 cities, the report provides initial insights for integration into participatory urban governance.
Keywords	Citizen-generated environmental data, Community engagement, Co-design, Citizen science, Creative practice, Creative commissioning, Inclusivity, Participatory governance

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the GA	
EU-R	Classified information - Restricted under EC Decision 2005/444	
EU-C	Classified information - Confidential under EC Decision 2005/444	

History			
Version	Date	Released by	Comment
0.1	01.09.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Draft structure
0.2	11.09.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Methodology v1
0.3	22.09.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Precedents and context v1
0.4	16.10.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Conceptual framework, rationale, workshop descriptions v1
0.5	20.10.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	References
0.6	21.10.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Methodology v2
0.7	1.12.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Dundee and Cascais activities. Cross city insights. Edit across all sections
0.8	17.12.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Acronyms, appendix, list of figures and tables
0.9	17.12.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN)	Executive Summary, Conclusion
0.9	17.12.2025	Gerid Hager (IIASA)	Review and suggested edits
1.0	18.12.2025	Mel Woods (UNIVDUN), Gerid Hager (IIASA)	Final version for submission

Project Partners

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Acronyms

CIC	Community Interest Company
CV	Curriculum Vitae
DG	Directorate-General (European Commission department)
GBI	Green-Blue Infrastructure
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
NEB	New European Bauhaus
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
ST+ARTS	Science, Technology and the Arts
UNBOXED	UNBOXED: Creativity in the UK (UK-wide cultural festival programme)

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Executive Summary

This document is a deliverable of the Urban ReLeaf project, which is co-funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101086638 and UKRI Innovate UK grant agreement numbers 10061290 and 10041792.

Task 2.3 Pop-Up Community and Culture Labs, encompasses the design, implementation and early outcomes within WP2 Stakeholder dialogue and inclusive citizen participation. The Pop-Up Labs were conceived as short-term, creative interventions enabling cities to translate citizen-generated environmental data into publicly accessible cultural experiences. The work aims to support community engagement and enhance awareness of citizen-generated environmental data through creative and artistic practices. This framework enables cities, with varying institutional capacities, to commission and support creative practitioners working with local communities to interpret environmental data through a range of creative formats.

The methodology was informed by precedent projects and is aligned with broader EU policy frameworks including the European Green Deal, the New European Bauhaus, and the EU Cities Mission. Implementation across the six Urban ReLeaf cities, Athens, Dundee, Utrecht, Cascais, Mannheim and Riga, follows a structured five-stage process: Preparation; Open Call & Commissioning; Engagement; Production; and Evaluation. As of this deliverable, cities are at different stages of implementation.

This deliverable provides:

- the conceptual and methodological foundations of the Pop-Up Labs;
- the implementation framework and resources developed for city partners;
- an interim overview of progress in each pilot city; and
- initial cross-city insights and recommendations for replication.

A synthesis of outcomes will be delivered in D2.4 Reflections and Insights Workshops. The tested creative commissioning framework will subsequently inform WP5's Urban ReLeaf Toolkit, contributing to wider guidance on embedding creative practice within inclusive, data-driven urban governance.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research. Urban ReLeaf is enabling citizens to gather environmental data, such as air quality measurements, heat stress indicators, biodiversity observations, perception mapping and narrative accounts in order to strengthen inclusive urban greening, expand data availability for decision-making, and broaden opportunities for citizen participation in environmental governance.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Across the six pilot cities, Athens, Dundee, Utrecht, Cascais, Mannheim and Riga, communities are generating diverse forms of environmental data that contribute to more locally grounded and socially responsive approaches to climate adaptation and urban green-space management. However, data can be difficult to interpret, unevenly accessible, or disconnected from everyday experience, especially for people unfamiliar with sensor and monitoring technologies or scientific terminology.

This creates a challenge, how can environmental data become meaningful across diverse groups and support wider public engagement and action?

Within Urban ReLeaf, WP2: Engagement and NAME Strategy addresses this challenge by developing inclusive guidelines for environmental data gathering, and actions that engage vulnerable communities, making environmental information more visible, relatable and publicly resonant. As part of WP2, Task 2.3 Community and Culture Pop-Up Labs, explores how creative and cultural practices can support communities and municipalities in interpreting environmental data. Creative methods,

such as visual art, performance, participatory design and public storytelling, offer alternative ways of representing environmental information, connecting it to lived experience, and fostering shared dialogue around urban environmental issues.

The Pop-Up Labs were therefore conceived as short-term, flexible interventions that can be embedded in existing community activities, festivals or public spaces. Their temporary and adaptive format allows cities to experiment with creative translations of data, reach new audiences, and activate environmental conversations in ways that complement longer-term monitoring and planning processes.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

This deliverable documents the design, implementation, and interim outcomes of Task 2.3. It provides:

- A consolidated conceptual and methodological framework for the Pop-Up Labs;
- An account of the tools, templates and commissioning processes developed and applied across cities;
- An interim overview of implementation across the six pilot cities;
- Preliminary insights and learning to inform cross-city comparison; and
- Early recommendations supporting future replication and integration into municipal governance.

The deliverable does not provide full cross-city comparative analysis or final evaluation. These will be conducted leading up to and during Task 2.4 Insights Workshops, once all six cities have completed their activities.

1.3 Alignment with the Workplan and Grant Agreement

This deliverable responds directly to the requirements of Task 2.3 Community and Culture Pop-Up Labs (Pop-Up Labs). Task 2.3 mandates the design, implementation and documentation of short-term, creative interventions that translate citizen-generated environmental data into publicly accessible cultural experiences. The work contributes to Urban ReLeaf's broader objectives to mobilise and empower local communities, integrate active and passive citizen data into urban monitoring and planning, and support inclusive governance approaches for green urban transitions.

The deliverable aligns with the work plan by:

- Documenting the design and operationalisation of a standardised yet flexible creative commissioning framework, including co-design workshops, transparent artist selection, structured mentoring and evaluation processes;
- Describing how this framework was applied across the six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities to develop place-based creative outputs informed by locally gathered environmental datasets;
- Presenting the preliminary results, learning and insights emerging from these activities to inform cross-city knowledge exchange; and

- Establishing early recommendations for synthesis in Task 2.4 Insights Workshops and WP5 (Urban ReLeaf Toolkit), where the creative commissioning methodology will be refined into replicable guidance for inclusion in participatory urban greening governance.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is organised into the following sections.

- **Section 1** introduces the background and purpose of the Pop-Up Labs and outlines their alignment with the Urban ReLeaf work plan.
- **Section 2** presents the conceptual and methodological framework underpinning the Pop-Up Labs, including theoretical foundations, precedent projects, EU policy alignment, and the commissioning and co-design methodology applied across cities.
- **Section 3** describes the ongoing implementation of the Pop-Up Labs in the six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities, documenting opportunity identification, co-design processes, community engagement, and the development of creative outputs.
- **Section 4** provides an interim synthesis and offers recommendations drawing on the methodological learning and emerging insights based on the pilot cities that have completed or initiated their Pop-Up Lab activities to date. Several commissions are scheduled to occur later due to seasonal or contextual factors, an evaluation will be conducted in Task 2.4 Insights Workshops.
- **Section 5** offers early recommendations for replication and for integrating creative practice into participatory environmental governance.

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2 Conceptual Framework and Rationale

Cities across Europe are increasingly engaging citizens in gathering, interpreting and applying environmental data and information to address climate-related challenges such as heat stress, air pollution, biodiversity loss and access to green space. While citizen science practices, scientific methods and citizen-generated data can enrich municipal datasets, and offer hyperlocal insights, a central challenge persists: participatory research and environmental information, whether sensor-based, mapped, thematic or narrative, rarely becomes meaningful or actionable for communities unless supported by processes that foster interpretation, dialogue and connection to place, lived experience and local priorities. Research in science and technology studies and environmental communication has shown that such meaning-making processes are often mediated through material, social and creative practices that situate data within everyday experience and local contexts (Gabrys, Hawkins & Michael, 2016).

Task 2.3 responds to this challenge by piloting Community and Culture Pop-Up Labs, which explore how creative and cultural practices can mediate between scientific practice, environmental information and public understanding. Across the Pop-Up Labs, this mediation does not always take the form of direct translation or use of Urban ReLeaf data; rather, creative practice frequently situates data within broader Urban ReLeaf topics, campaigns and locally relevant environmental concerns. This section outlines a research-informed framework for creative mediation that encompasses citizen-generated data, scientific knowledge and thematic environmental issues, from the conceptual foundations, policy alignment and precedent projects that inform the approach.

2.1 Conceptual framing for the Pop-Up Lab methodology

Scientific practices and technical data often remain inaccessible to non-experts due to barriers such as unfamiliar terminology, low data literacy, technical interfaces or limited opportunities for collective interpretation. Research in socially engaged art, participatory design, and environmental communication demonstrates that creative and cultural methods can help overcome these barriers by engaging people through sensory, visual, narrative or embodied forms of engagement that support collective meaning-making (Gabrys, Hawkins & Michael, 2016; Kester, 2011).

Within environmental governance and climate communication, creative practice is frequently positioned as secondary or “surface” activities, applied late in processes primarily for dissemination or visual appeal. This framing has limited the capacity of scientific and technical approaches to engage diverse publics, particularly in relation to climate and environmental challenges where data alone has struggled to inspire understanding or action. Urban ReLeaf responds to this structural gap by recognising creative and cultural practice as a necessary complement to scientific knowledge and citizen science approaches, rather than an add-on to it. By repositioning creative practice as integral to interpretation and engagement, the Pop-Up Lab methodology

addresses persistent limitations in how environmental data and knowledge is communicated, understood and acted upon in urban contexts.

Bishop (2012) highlights that participatory art creates conditions for collective engagement and meaning-making, enabling publics to interact with complex issues in accessible and situated ways. Similarly, Sanders and Stappers (2008) describe how co-creation processes support shared inquiry and enable participants to shape both the questions and representations emerging from design activities. In environmental communication research, Cox (2013) argues that narrative, visibility and affective engagement are crucial for supporting wider public involvement in environmental issues.

Creative practices therefore support environmental engagement by:

- **Making the invisible visible** - Artistic representation can reveal environmental processes, such as air pollution, that lack visibility in everyday life.
- **Supporting affective and experiential understanding** - Creative outputs link environmental measurements to emotions, memory and cultural identity.
- **Generating shared meaning** - Co-designed processes can provide structured opportunities for citizens, artists and municipal actors to explore data together.
- **Increasing accessibility and inclusion** - Creative engagement approaches lower participation thresholds for groups under-represented in technical or policy-oriented processes.

This conceptual grounding aligns with Gabrys' (2016) concept of data citizenship, which emphasises the relational and interpretive work required for communities to mobilise data as civic actors. It also resonates with Manzini's (2015) framing of social innovation, in which collaborative creativity becomes a means of collective reflection and local problem-solving.

Urban ReLeaf therefore positions creative practice not as a communication tool, but as a mode of knowledge-making that complements technical analysis and supports more inclusive, just and locally relevant governance. The conceptual phases outlined above are operationalised through a structured implementation framework, detailed in Section 3.

2.2 Policy context and alignment with EU priorities

The Pop-Up Labs directly support several major EU policy frameworks promoting citizen participation, inclusive climate neutrality transitions and place-based sustainability.

European Green Deal emphasises fair, inclusive processes for achieving climate neutrality. Pop-Up Labs contribute to these aims by enabling communities to engage meaningfully with environmental issues through culturally accessible forms of data interpretation and dialogue.

New European Bauhaus (NEB) promotes an integrated vision of sustainability through:

- Beautiful - aesthetic and cultural relevance,
- Sustainable - supporting ecological literacy and behavioural change, and
- Together participatory and community-driven approaches.

Pop-Up Labs operationalise NEB principles by translating environmental data into creative, place-sensitive outputs developed through co-creation.

EU Cities Mission: Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities stresses the importance of citizen engagement in achieving climate goals. The Pop-Up Labs offer cities:

- Short, agile commissioning cycles that can be embedded in community events;
- Mechanisms for involving residents in interpreting environmental data used in planning and adaptation strategies;
- Replicable methods that support Climate City Contract implementation.

Task 2.3 purposefully aligns with high-level EU ambitions and provides practical, transferable models at neighbourhood scale.

2.3 Precedent projects

The design of the Pop-Up Labs builds on more than a decade of experimentation at the intersection of citizen science, creative practice and environmental engagement. Several major initiatives previously designed and led by the main author of this deliverable provide an important methodological and operational foundation for Urban ReLeaf. A table that outlines the analysis and lessons learnt from these precedents is provided in Appendix 1.

Making Sense (2015–2018)

Making Sense explored community-led environmental sensing across several European cities, combining low-cost sensor technologies with creative engagement formats including interactive artefacts, sound walks, festivals and participatory mapping. The project demonstrated that creative processes can help communities make sense of complex environmental information by supporting trust-building, contextual interpretation and sustained participation Making Sense (2018), Coulson, S., Woods, M. (2018). Making Sense received international recognition, including being shortlisted for the STARTS Prize 2017 (Science + Technology + Arts) awarded by Ars Electronica on behalf of the European Commission.

GROW Observatory (2016–2019)

The GROW Observatory established one of Europe's largest citizen science networks focused on soil and climate monitoring. Alongside scientific activities, the project commissioned several high-impact art–science collaborations. Among these, 'By the Code of Soil' (Molga & Scanner, 2017) translated Earth Observation

and soil moisture data into audiovisual experiences and was exhibited at the Centre Pompidou (Paris) and the British Academy (London).

This work highlighted the importance of accessible data formats for creative practice and demonstrated the value of commissioning and mentoring structures that support high-quality, community-responsive creative outputs (GROW Observatory, 2019).

Dandelion (UNBOXED, 2022)

Dandelion was part of the UK-wide UNBOXED festival, it developed a programme of creative micro-grants, community gardens, public installations and participatory events exploring climate, food and sustainability. The Unexpected Gardens commissions were widely acknowledged for their community impact and creative innovation, including detailed delivery, coverage and analysis by University of Dundee and Creative Dundee (2022). The project demonstrated how modest, flexible creative commissions, supported by strong local partnerships, can foster inclusive environmental engagement in diverse communities.

2.4 Principles guiding the Pop-Up Labs

Insights from the precedent projects directly informed the principles underpinning the Urban ReLeaf Pop-Up Lab framework. The main author's experience in delivering these projects provided continuity and shaped key conceptual and operational decisions. The Pop-Up Labs are guided by the following principles:

2.4.1 Transparency and ethics

Commissioning processes, selection criteria and decision-making procedures are transparent, following an open process, and documented. Ethical considerations related to environmental data and participant engagement are integrated throughout, ensuring fairness, accountability and responsible innovation.

2.4.2 Inclusivity and accessibility

Pop-Up Labs are designed to remove barriers to participation by using accessible creative formats and accommodating different linguistic, cultural and physical needs. Activities aim to engage diverse groups, including those underrepresented in traditional participatory processes.

2.4.3 Context sensitivity

Creative outputs respond to the environmental, cultural and social characteristics of each neighbourhood and city. This principle ensures that activities are locally relevant to the Urban ReLeaf campaign, reflect community priorities and acknowledge the specific cultural opportunities of place.

2.4.4 Feasibility and Sustainability

Pop-Up Lab activities must be delivered within available resources, timeframes and local constraints, while enabling outputs with the potential for ongoing community value. Practical feasibility, including permissions, materials, seasonal limitations, capacity and in-kind support, is considered from the outset.

The precedent projects described above informed several core design decisions within the Pop-Up Lab methodology. Their use of lightweight, temporary formats demonstrated the value of short, flexible creative interventions for stimulating wider participation and public awareness. Their integration of environmental sensor data, narrative or visual interpretation helped to shape the emphasis on translation and accessibility within the commissioning framework. Furthermore, the precedents illustrated the importance of supporting community experience, which reinforced the participatory, rather than co-created, ethos of the Pop-Up Labs. These insights provided a foundation upon which the Urban ReLeaf methodology was developed.

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3 Methodology and Implementation Framework

This section presents the Pop-Up Lab methodology developed under Task 2.3, detailing the implementation of the five-phase structure, commissioning approach, tools and templates, and the ethical and operational considerations that support implementation across cities. The methodology has been informed by precedent project analysis (Section 2), and iterative co-development during the General Assembly workshops in Utrecht and Cascais (Section 4).

The Pop-Up Lab model is designed to be structured yet adaptable, providing cities with a clear process, allowing flexibility to respond to local governance contexts, community needs, seasonal conditions and resource availability.

3.1 Operationalisation of the five-phase Pop-Up Lab methodology

The Implementation structure, tools, roles and timelines of the Pop-Up Lab model follows a **five-phase delivery process** that supports cities to identify opportunities, commission creative practitioners, engage communities, produce creative outputs and reflect on learning (see Figure 1). Initial workshop sessions, to clarify the aims, objectives, definitions, precedent projects and structure of the Pop-Up Labs is followed by the full cycle, recommended to take at least a 14–18 weeks, with cities adapting timelines to fit local governance, cultural calendars and operational contexts.

Phase 1 Preparation (weeks 1 – 2)

Cities begin by reviewing relevant pilot topics and local environmental themes, as well as citizen-generated environmental datasets, mapping potential partners and venues, and assessing practical constraints. The preparation phase also includes identifying existing community events or public spaces where Pop-Up Lab activities could be woven in, reducing logistical and resource barriers. The short two-week window supports rapid mobilisation while providing space to prepare the open call documents, eligibility and selection guidance, and communications strategy. This foundational work helps ensure feasibility and local relevance before commissioning begins.

Phase 2 Open call and commissioning (Weeks 3 – 9)

To align with best practice, and maximise reach and inclusivity, an open call process was adapted from resources adapted from prior projects. Cities issue an open call inviting creative practitioners to propose participatory creative activities that interpret selected environmental data themes. This phase includes eligibility checks, transparent selection criteria, panel assessment, interviews (as required). Commissions were valued at €2.500,--, covering artist fees, materials and community engagement activities. This micro-commission model was designed to support short-term, publicly visible creative interventions while remaining feasible within diverse municipal contexts. In addition to the direct commission, cities provided significant in-kind support, including coordination, access to community partners, venues, communications and technical assistance. Cities had the opportunity to supplement the Urban ReLeaf allocation with additional local funding to support specific objectives (see Table 1).

Table 1 Indicative budget structure

Item	Proportion	Amount	Example activity
Artist Fee	40%	€1,000	Commission (5 x days at €200 day rate)
Materials	40%	€1,000	Specific to the proposal and activities
Engagement	20%	€500	Artist engagement e.g. workshop with community groups and city stakeholders, refreshments etc
Evaluation	In-kind		Review of submissions, interview panel, feedback, evaluation
Design and Communications Services	In-kind		Design materials, graphics, evaluation, documentation and social media
City Support	In-kind		Support to organise, promote events and public engagement e.g. city events and festivals, use of local authority, public or community spaces.
Discretionary Budget	%	≤ €1,000	Discretionary budget increase for additional objectives set by the local authority

The six-week duration accommodates dissemination, proposal development, submission, review and contracting. The commissioning process prioritises fairness, clarity and accessibility, enabling a broad range of practitioners to participate.

The **submission and selection procedure** was standardised across all six cities to ensure transparency and fairness.

Process overview:

Submission handling – Cities created a dedicated *City* folder on the project repository and logged all proposals using a SharePoint template.

Eligibility check – Applications verified for completeness (CV, budget, proposal).

Review panel composition:

- 1 University of Dundee representative (task lead)
- 1 City team member
- 1 Urban ReLeaf partner

Table 2 Scoring criteria (0 - 2 scale)

Criterion	Weight	Description
Community engagement approach	35 %	Depth, inclusivity, accessibility
Communication & creativity	25 %	Quality and originality
Budget feasibility & delivery plan	20 %	Practical and realistic
Track record	20 %	Evidence of skills and experience

Shortlisting and Interview – Top 3–4 applicants invited for 20–30 minute interview, including a 7–10 minute presentation of past work. All artists received identical questions to ensure consistency.

Final selection – Panel aggregated scores and agreed on the awardee.

Documentation – All stages and scores were recorded for reporting and auditing. This transparent selection system met Horizon Europe standards for inclusivity, accountability, and reproducibility across partner cities.

Phase 3 Engagement and Development (Weeks 10–14)

Artists conduct participatory engagement activities with local communities. These activities vary by city but may include workshops, conversations, sensory walks, mapping exercises, public drop-ins or short participatory experiments. The emphasis is on supporting communities to interpret environmental data in ways that relate to their lived experience and local concerns. The four-week engagement window provides time for meaningful interaction while maintaining momentum. In-kind support from city partners is essential during this period to facilitate outreach, logistics and accessibility.

Phase 4 Production and presentation (Weeks 14–16)

Based on insights gathered during the Engagement phase, creative practitioners produce the final artistic work. Outputs may include public installations, performances, digital artefacts, murals, participatory visualisations or temporary interventions in public space. Cities provide logistical support, permissions, materials and communications assistance as required. Production and presentation may overlap with late-stage engagement activities, reflecting the pop-up nature of the model, which prioritises low-complexity, high-visibility creative interventions that can be delivered with modest resources.

Phase 5 – Evaluation and Reflection (Weeks 17–18)

Cities and practitioners evaluate the Pop-Up Lab process using shared templates and reflective tools. Evaluation focuses on community relevance, environmental understanding, feasibility and potential for legacy. Documentation tasks include capturing outcomes, gathering feedback from artists and participants, and synthesising learning for local Insight Workshops and future methodological refinement.

The practical implications of this adaptability for local implementation are outlined further in Section 3.5.

Figure 1 Pop-Up Lab five-phase process showing the suggested timeline, actions and responsibilities at each phase

3.2 Roles and Responsibilities Across the Pop-Up Lab Process

Delivery of the Pop-Up Labs relies on coordinated roles shared between city pilot teams, the Task 2.3 lead, commissioned creative practitioners, community partners and participants. These roles also carry shared responsibility for ethical, inclusive and accessible delivery, as outlined in Section 3.3.

Commissioning partner

UNIVDUN provides overarching methodological guidance, including development of tools and templates, facilitation of co-design workshops and advisory support throughout implementation. The WP2 lead monitors consistency across cities, supports ethical and accessible practice, and synthesises cross-city learning.

City Pilot Teams

City teams lead local delivery by refining environmental themes, adapting the Open Call template, coordinating dissemination, convening selection panels, and providing in-kind support such as venues, communications and logistical assistance. They ensure alignment with municipal procedures and Urban ReLeaf's ethical framework, and act as the primary contact point for practitioners.

Creative Practitioners

Commissioned practitioners design and deliver participatory engagement, interpret themes and datasets through creative practice, and produce a feasible final output. They work closely with city teams to ensure activities are aligned with the proposal.

Community Partners and Local Organisations

Partners assist with outreach, venue support, contextual input and strengthening inclusion. Their involvement helps ensure activities are accessible, locally grounded and responsive to community needs.

A suite of resources supports each phase of delivery, ensuring a transparent, consistent methodology across cities while allowing for local adaptation. These resources, developed from precedent project insights and workshop input, are summarised in Table 3 and provided in the Appendix. The following section describes how these tools are operationalised during the Preparation phase through a structured co-design workshop methodology.

Table 3 Pop-Up Labs process showing phases, key tools and purpose

Phases	Key tool type	Purpose	Location
Preparation	Feasibility Matrix, Outputs Matrix, Commissioning Guide Call for Creative Proposals template	Determine viable themes and formats	Appendix
Open Call Commission	Eligibility Checklist, Interview Templates, Shortlisting and Interview Scoring Templates	Transparent submission and selection process	Appendix
Engagement	In-kind support including mentoring and meetings, a communication plan	Practitioner support, engagement of communities	Communications Plan
Production	Event preparation checklist	Public event	Internal
Evaluation	Evaluation Template	Reporting and best practice	Internal

3.3 Co-design and preparation workshops

A set of shared co-design tools supports the workshop process and provides a common analytical foundation across cities. These tools are designed to guide the collaborative identification of local opportunities, assess feasibility and guide early planning decisions:

- **City Cultural Opportunity Map** Used to document existing creative assets, cultural events, community networks and potential venues that could host or amplify Pop-Up Lab activities.
- **Creative Outputs Matrix** Applied to explore a range of possible artistic and cultural formats and to anticipate their practical, technical and social implications within local contexts.
- **Impact and Feasibility Matrix** Used to assess emerging ideas according to their anticipated community impact, inclusivity potential and logistical or resource feasibility.

These tools allow each city to respond to its specific cultural, institutional and environmental conditions. Full templates are provided in the Appendix.

Workshop methodology and analytical process

The workshop methodology combines facilitated activities and structured analysis to support cities in progressing from broad ambitions to prioritised Pop-Up Lab concepts.

Workshops begin with context setting and data landscape review, during which city teams reflect on local environmental conditions, existing community initiatives and available datasets, such as citizen sensor data, perception mapping or municipal environmental data. This establishes a shared understanding of local opportunities and constraints.

A **future-oriented visioning exercise** then invites participants to consider what a successful Pop-Up Lab would look like one year after delivery, including desired community impacts, visibility and forms of creative engagement. This activity supports the identification of success for the team, and alignment around shared values such as accessibility, relevance and inclusivity.

Cities then undertake **people, skills and partnership mapping**, identifying relevant creative practitioners, cultural organisations and community-facing partners. This process informs decisions about appropriate engagement formats and contributes to the development of **Cultural Opportunity Maps**.

Emerging ideas are subsequently assessed through **impact and feasibility analysis**. City teams map potential Pop-Up Lab opportunities against two dimensions:

- Impact, including potential for community engagement, inclusivity, visibility and alignment with Urban ReLeaf objectives; and
- Feasibility, including resource availability, permissions, technical complexity, time constraints and partnership readiness.

This structured assessment supports transparent prioritisation of ideas that are both meaningful and achievable within the micro-commission model. The process results in a set of priority opportunities that inform the development of city-specific Open Call briefs and commissioning criteria.

These activities can be delivered for teams in-person or through online collaborative environments such as Miro. These workshop activities operationalise the Preparation phase of the Pop-Up Lab methodology and support consistent yet locally responsive planning across all pilot cities.

3.4 Ethical, inclusive and accessible practice

All Pop-Up Lab activities are delivered in accordance with Urban ReLeaf's strategy for the inclusion of vulnerable communities outlined in D2.2 Strategy blueprints for Urban ReLeaf city pilots.

Ethical governance and data responsibility

Pop-Up Labs are designed to reflect citizen science practices and to work primarily with citizen-generated environmental data and creative interpretation, rather than personal or sensitive data, therefore no personal data are collected.

Creative practitioners are supported to interpret environmental data responsibly, avoiding misleading representation or overstated claims. City teams and the Task 2.3 lead provide guidance to ensure that any artistic translations of data remain appropriate for public engagement.

Inclusive and accessible engagement

Inclusivity and accessibility are embedded as minimum delivery standards across all Pop-Up Labs. Activities are designed to reduce barriers to participation and to engage a broad range of community members, including groups under-represented in technical, scientific or policy-led processes.

Key considerations include:

- physical and sensory accessibility of venues and public spaces;
- clarity and accessibility of language and communication materials;
- cultural and social sensitivity to local community contexts;
- selection of creative formats that support varied levels of confidence, literacy and experience;
- timing and location of activities to align with community availability and existing public events.

City teams are responsible for identifying and addressing accessibility considerations during the preparation phase, including the selection of appropriate venues, formats and local partners. Where necessary, in-kind support is provided to enable inclusive delivery, such as access to community spaces, facilitation support, or communications assistance.

3.5 Integrating flexibility and local adaptation

Building on the indicative timeline introduced in Section 3.1.2, the methodology incorporates a high degree of flexibility to ensure feasibility and relevance across diverse municipal contexts. While the five-phase structure provides a coherent framework for planning and delivery, cities are expected to implement the process with adjustments that reflect their local realities. These may arise from community availability and local event calendars, municipal procedures such as permissions or contracting requirements, seasonal or weather-related factors affecting outdoor activities, alignment with existing cultural programmes, or the working patterns and networks of commissioned practitioners.

The indicative timeline therefore functions as a guiding structure rather than a prescriptive schedule. It establishes a shared rhythm across the consortium while allowing cities the necessary space to tailor implementation to their operational, cultural and environmental conditions. This adaptability is essential for ensuring that Pop-Up Labs remain feasible and impactful across varied urban settings.

The methodology is designed as a structured yet responsive process that supports cities in translating scientific practices and citizen-generated and municipal environmental data into creative and socially embedded outcomes. It provides a clear progression, from opportunity definition to commissioning, engagement and final creative presentation, while accommodating the practical considerations that shape local delivery. The accompanying tools and resources offer guidance at each stage, enabling consistency in approach while allowing the method to respond sensitively to local priorities, constraints and opportunities.

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4 Application of the Pop-Up Lab methodology across cities

This section documents the application of the five-phase Pop-Up Lab methodology across the six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities. While Section 3 outlines the methodological framework and tools, Section 4 focuses on how cities engaged with these resources. First through collective co-design workshops in Utrecht and Cascais, and subsequently through city-specific planning and commissioning processes. This section does not assess outcomes, which are addressed in Section 5, but instead explains how the methodology was embedded within pilot cities and prepared for delivery.

4.1 Co-Design development workshops

The application of the Pop-Up Lab methodology began with two co-design workshops held during the Urban ReLeaf General Assemblies in Utrecht and Cascais, involving representatives from all pilot cities. The workshops provided a shared starting point for implementation, enabling city teams to engage collectively with the Pop-Up Lab framework and to begin adapting it to their local contexts (see Figure 2).

Through the workshops, cities explored ambitions, opportunities and practical constraints relevant to their local environments and governance settings. Outputs from these sessions informed the initial definition of city-specific Pop-Up Lab themes and supported early decision-making in advance of commissioning.

As a final step, city teams developed a first draft of their Pop-Up Lab plans using a collaborative online workspace (see Figure 3). These initial concepts formed the basis for subsequent refinement and were translated into city-specific Open Calls and commissioning documents.

City pilot planning (30 minutes)

Divide into groups for each city, colleagues join a city table, Miro step by step:

- Brainstorm potential lab activities, prioritise the exploration of citizen-generated data.
- Identify relevant creative disciplines needed to realise these ideas (e.g., visual arts, digital and interactive media, designer, performance art, poet, filmmaker, architect).
- Timeline for workshops aligned with your planned activity
- Preferred output or outcomes and benefits.

Activity

12

Figure 2 City pilot planning activity instructions

Outcome of the workshops

Following delivery of the two workshops, the cities progressed from initial engagement with the Pop-Up Lab framework to active preparation for delivery. The collaborative groundwork established during the General Assembly sessions enabled each city to define a locally grounded Pop-Up Lab concept and establish a clear pathway towards commissioning and implementation. Section 4.2 outlines how cities built on this early planning to progress through preparation, commissioning and delivery stages, highlighting variations in governance structures, datasets, engagement opportunities and resource contexts.

4.2 Pop-Up Labs local phased implementation

Following the co-design workshops held during the Utrecht and Cascais General Assemblies, city pilot teams progressed into the **Preparation phase** of the Pop-Up Lab methodology. Building on the shared framework, cities refined locally relevant themes (see table 4), identified suitable delivery contexts, and adapted the Open Call for Creative Proposals to reflect local datasets, cultural priorities and accessibility considerations. Opportunities were then disseminated through Urban ReLeaf communication channels and city-specific outreach plans.

Table 4 Overview of the initial Pop-Up Lab opportunities developed by each pilot city, summarising themes, data sources and community contexts

City	Opportunity	Theme and Data	Community Context / Motivation
Athens	Air-quality interactive	Citizen-sensor and municipal pollution data	Raise awareness of urban air pollution and greening
Cascais	Greenspace thermal-comfort and shade mapping through participatory poems	Perception mapping data, temperature and relative humidity data & citizen perception surveys	Demonstrating lived experience of heat and cooling
Dundee	Green blue perceptions represented on co-created lanterns	Green-Blue Infrastructure and perception mapping	Strengthen connection between parks and public health
Mannheim	Interactive interpretation of tree data	Tree mapping and planting	
Riga	Air Quality place-based Mural	Citizen-recorded Air Quality data	Promote citizen stewardship
Utrecht	Neighbourhood heat-stress	Citizen sensors & comfort, and hot spot mapping	Empower communities in vulnerable housing areas

Cities subsequently initiated the **Open Call and Commissioning phase**, managing submissions and selection activities in line with the shared procedures outlined in Section 3. As cities progressed through these early stages, commissioned practitioners were appointed and preparatory coordination for engagement and delivery began where timelines allowed.

Cities are progressing through the Pop-Up Lab phases at different paces, shaped by local governance procedures, cultural calendars and operational contexts. This variation reflects the flexible design of the methodology, which supports locally feasible delivery within a shared framework. The subsections that follow therefore present each city's current stage of development, highlighting where in the Pop-Up Lab process they are currently. To support comparability across the consortium, each city's Pop-Up Lab is described using a consistent structure aligned with the five methodological phases (see Table 5). Where cities have progressed into commissioning, engagement or early production activities, these are included as illustrations of implementation. Other cities are completing preparation and commissioning activities that will inform subsequent delivery cycles.

To aid clarity, the following subsections are grouped into three categories:

- **Completed Commissions**
Cities that have delivered their Pop-Up Lab outputs (e.g., Dundee, Cascais).
- **In-Progress Commissions**
Cities where the call has been announced, and development is underway (e.g., Utrecht, Mannheim).
- **Scheduled Commissions**
Cities where the open call will be launched later due to justified contextual factors (e.g., Athens and Riga—mural requiring warmer weather).

Table 5 Overview of creativity and culture Pop-Up Lab timelines by city, showing completed, in progress and scheduled phases.

City	Co-design Workshop	Preparation	Open call	Engagement	Production	Evaluation
Athens	✓	In progress	Scheduled	Scheduled	Scheduled	Scheduled
Cascais	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	In progress
Dundee	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	In progress
Mannheim	✓	✓	In progress	Scheduled	Scheduled	Scheduled
Riga	✓	In progress	Scheduled	Scheduled	Scheduled	Scheduled
Utrecht	✓	✓	✓	Scheduled	Scheduled	Scheduled

4.3 Dundee Pop-Up Lab

4.3.1 Local context, rationale and key decisions

Dundee focused its Pop-Up Lab on perceptions of the city's green and blue spaces, drawing on data collected through the Urban ReLeaf perceptions app and paper surveys. These data capture how residents experience local greenspaces, what they value, where they feel safe, and what could be improved, and are being integrated into Dundee's wider Open Greenspace Mapping and policy reporting processes. The city selected this theme due to the strong alignment between community perceptions, ongoing greenspace strategy work, and the opportunity to foreground both blue and green assets during a major public event. The theme also complemented the city's ambition to make environmental data more accessible through artistic and participatory processes.

During the preparation phase, Dundee city pilot team prioritised community groups that could benefit from accessible, creative engagement, including residents from vulnerable or underrepresented communities. A key consideration was the requirement to align the final creative output with Dundee's St Andrew's Day "Hooley" event on 30 November, which set a fixed production timeline and influenced the output type, venue availability and workshop scheduling. The city also determined that the commission should deliver a defined final output, a series of illuminated lanterns for the parade, ensuring visibility within the event and compatibility with festival logistics. While this more prescribed outcome narrowed the creative scope, it provided clarity for applicants and ensured that the work could be feasibly produced within the available timeframe.

4.3.2 Commissioning selected practitioner(s), production and presentation

The commission was awarded to What Moves You CIC, led by Dawn Hartley and Niamh O'Loughlin, two experienced dance and engagement specialists with significant expertise in participatory, community-centred creative practice. Their proposal, described in detail in their submission, **Lantern Artist submissions**, offered a sequence of lantern-making workshops incorporating movement, sensory exercises and collaborative making, designed to be inclusive for participants of all ages and abilities. The selection panel valued the team's **proven track record of community engagement** and their ability to create welcoming, supportive environments for participants with varying levels of experience.

Participants produced a vibrant collection **140 illuminated lanterns** for the parade. Each expressed **individuals' creativity** incorporating motifs inspired by water, foliage and interconnection, echoing Dundee's environmental landscape and the artists' interest in linking participants symbolically through light. The city provided logistical support for installation, lighting preparation and safe handling during the parade. The lanterns collectively became a high-visibility public expression of community participation and celebration, marking the culmination of the Dundee Pop-Up Lab's creative cycle.

4.3.3 Early Insights, In-kind Support, partnerships and reflections

City staff noted that **identifying a dedicated internal liaison** was critical for coordinating in-kind support efficiently and resolving procedural or logistical challenges. The **clearly defined output**, lanterns for a fixed event, streamlined delivery but **led to fewer open call applications**, suggesting that **more open-ended commissions may attract a wider creative range** in future cycles. The workshops effectively **engaged residents who might not typically take part in participatory arts activities**, demonstrating the value of accessible formats and partnerships with trusted practitioners. While data integration was limited, the Lab contributed meaningfully to awareness, community connection and visibility of greenspace themes ahead of policy reporting. Figures 4-7 provide a visual documentation of the activities.

Dundee City Council provided substantial in-kind contributions including:

- staff time for coordination and partner liaison
- support with venue access and bookings
- communications and promotional activity
- materials support and troubleshooting
- an additional £1,000 to supplement production costs

These contributions ensured that workshops were adequately resourced and that the final output was aligned with the Hooley event schedule and safety requirements.

Figure 4 Volunteers adding lights to 140 lanterns

Figure 5 Citizens gather at the start for the lanterns procession

Figure 6 Citizens carrying their lanterns in the procession

Figure 7 Drone footage of Hooley procession showing Urban ReLeaf participations

4.4 Cascais Pop-Up Lab

4.4.1 Local Context, rationale and key decisions

Cascais centred its Pop-Up Lab on public perceptions of heat stress and cooling in greenspaces, reflecting both growing municipal interest in urban heat mitigation and citizen-generated insights collected through the Urban ReLeaf Perceptions App and paper surveys. These datasets were complemented by local temperature and relative humidity measurements, enabling the city to compare subjective experiences of heat with sensor-validated microclimate conditions.

The city identified **seven key parks** across Cascais as the spatial focus for the Pop-Up Lab, informed by their public use, ecological functions and cooling potential. **Themes of shade, trees, greenery and thermal comfort** were prioritised due to their relevance to climate adaptation strategies and ongoing urban greening programmes. During the preparation phase, Cascais refined its approach using the shared tools, including assessing which parks were logistically suitable for workshops.

A key decision was to pursue a poetry and illustration-based commission, reflecting the city's strong literary culture (including an active local book club) and the desire for a creative output that could be installed directly in parks to encourage ongoing public engagement. The city also recognised early that recruitment of participants, particularly from vulnerable or harder-to-reach communities, would be challenging. An internal staff member was assigned to support recruitment and coordination, which proved important for overcoming early engagement barriers.

4.4.2 Commissioning, Selected Practitioner, Production and Presentation

The Open Call was adapted from the WP2 template and disseminated locally, inviting proposals that could creatively interpret citizens' experiences of heat, shade, and comfort across the seven selected greenspaces. Following the submission process, the commission was awarded to Alexandra Dias, a Cascais-based visual artist and poet known for expressive post-impressionist painting and published poetry collections, with extensive experience in community-facing work and event facilitation.

Dias proposed a series of poetry workshops, one in each of the seven parks, inviting participants to explore their embodied experiences of heat, shade, comfort and cooling. The workshops used sensory prompts, guided reflection and creative writing to support participants in articulating emotional and physical encounters with greenspace microclimates. The artist also proposed a compiled book of poems and illustrations celebrating the parks' cooling qualities and the human-nature relationship.

Engagement activities were delivered across the parks as planned, though in some initial activities public turnout was lower than anticipated. Several municipal staff also participated, creating unexpected internal benefits by strengthening interdepartmental connections and shared understanding of greenspace issues.

For the final output, Cascais ran a poetry competition, selecting four poems from workshop contributions and wider submissions. These were installed directly in parks,

allowing residents and visitors to encounter the creative reflections in situ and encouraging further dialogue about heat, comfort and the value of green infrastructure.

4.4.3 Early Insights, In-Kind Support, Partnerships and Reflections

Cascais provided in-kind support, including staff time for coordination, venue booking permissions, workshop organisation, communications, materials procurement and assistance with installing the final poems in parks. Partnerships with local cultural groups, such as the Cascais book club, were explored as potential amplifiers of participation and visibility, although engagement from target community groups remained limited.

A key reflection emerged around participant recruitment: the clearly defined output, poetry, appealed strongly to some audiences but discouraged broader community participation, particularly among groups less familiar with creative writing. This reduced the diversity of voices represented in the engagement process. However, the involvement of municipal staff produced positive internal outcomes, helping staff reflect on greenspace experiences from both professional and personal perspectives.

The Pop-Up Lab also highlighted the value of having a designated internal coordinator, who played a crucial role in overcoming logistical challenges and sustaining momentum through the engagement phase. Despite lower-than-planned community turnout, the final outputs contributed to increased visibility of greenspaces and heat-related themes within the city, and created tangible, park-based interventions that can support future communication and engagement activities.

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Urban ReLeaf

Urban ReLeaf em Cascais

O Urban ReLeaf é um projeto europeu que une ciência cidadã, monitorização ambiental e experiências artísticas para tornar as cidades mais resilientes às alterações climáticas. Em Cascais, convidámos a comunidade a transformar o calor, a sombra, a brisa e a luz dos parques urbanos em poesia.

Ao longo de vários meses, moradores, curiosos e amantes das palavras participaram em oficinas poéticas nos parques da Abóboda, Quinta da Carreira, Penado e Jardim Visconde da Luz. Outros parques contaram com a sensibilidade de colegas da Câmara Municipal de Cascais e da Cascais Ambiente, que deram voz aos lugares.

Cada poema é uma resposta única à relação entre corpo e ambiente, entre cidade e sensação, entre verão e memória.

Mais do que textos, estas criações são um retrato vivo da ligação entre pessoas e espaços verdes da vila, mostrando que a poesia pode crescer silenciosa, firme e cheia de vida mesmo na pressa da cidade.

É nestes parques que o calor, a sombra, a brisa e a luz se transformaram em versos — cada espaço com a sua própria voz e história.

Para saber mais sobre o projeto, visite o site

www.urbanreleaf.eu
@releafcities #ReleafCities

Urban ReLeaf

Urban ReLeaf in Cascais

Urban ReLeaf is a European project that combines citizen science, environmental monitoring, and artistic experiences to make cities more resilient to climate change.

In Cascais, we invited the community to transform the heat, shade, breeze, and light of urban parks into poetry.

Over several months, residents, curious visitors, and poetry enthusiasts took part in workshops at the parks of Abóboda, Quinta da Carreira, Penado, and Visconde da Luz. Other parks drew on the sensitivity of colleagues from the Cascais City Council and Cascais Ambiente, who gave voice to the spaces.

Each poem is a unique response to the relationship between body and environment, city and sensation, summer and memory.

More than texts, these creations form a living portrait of the connection between people and the town's green spaces, showing that poetry can grow quietly, firmly, and full of life, even amidst the pace of the city.

It is in these parks that heat, shade, breeze, and light were transformed into verses — each space with its own voice and story.

To find out more about the project, visit the website

www.urbanreleaf.eu
@releafcities #ReleafCities

Versos em Exaltação: Poesia entre o Calor Urbano

Jardim Visconde da Luz — Memória, Sombra e Caminhos da

Inaugurado em 1867, o Jardim Visconde da Luz é um refúgio verde no coração de Cascais, com árvores ornamentais, fontes e monumentos, incluindo o Monumento aos Mortos da Grande Guerra.

Aqui, a história, a sombra e o lazer coexistem, oferecendo um espaço onde o tempo abranda e a poesia encontra lugar.

No workshop, os autores inspiraram-se na frase: "A cidade transpira poesia, as árvores falam em verso, em mim florescem palavras."

Jardim Visconde da Luz — Memory, Shade and Paths of the Town

Visconde da Luz Garden, inaugurated in 1867, is a historic and romantic green refuge in the heart of Cascais. Named after Joaquim António Velez Barreiros, the Viscount of Luz, it preserves ornamental trees, fountains, and monuments, including the World War I Memorial. The garden blends history, shade, and leisure, offering a space where time slows, nature and urban life meet, and poetry finds a home.

Here, workshop participants reflected on the city's voice, inspired by: "The city exhales poetry, the trees speak in verse, and words bloom within me."

**No silêncio do jardim,
Sou luz que guia a escuridão,
entre a memória e a modernidade,
sou raiz, sou voz, sou canção.**

**A cidade transpira poesia,
As árvores falam em verso,
Em mim florescem palavras,
E cada folha guarda um universo.**

**Assim caminho, em paz e harmonia,
Pois cada passo é sonho que ilumina,
E cada olhar, um livro que se cria.**

Lurdes Vaz

Figure 8 Cascais Jardim Visconde park signage and poem by Lurdes Vaz

4.5 Utrecht Pop-Up Lab

4.5.1 Local context, rationale and early-stage commissioning process

Utrecht's Pop-Up Lab was framed around the lived experience of urban heat in neighbourhoods with limited greenery, building directly on citizen-generated data from the Green Neighbourhood, Cool Neighbourhood programme. Residents in Kanaleneiland, Rivierenwijk, Ondiep and Zuilen had collected temperature, humidity and qualitative "heat experience" data during recent summer periods, creating a rich evidence base that combines sensor data with personal perception. The city and project partners identified an opportunity to translate these insights into a public-facing, creative format that could make climate data tangible, accessible and emotionally resonant for a broader audience, while foregrounding issues of climate justice and uneven exposure to heat stress.

At this early stage, Utrecht's key strategic decision was to focus the Pop-Up Lab on framing and advertising an open creative opportunity, rather than predefining outputs or formats. An open call was developed inviting Utrecht-based artists, designers and other creatives with experience in participatory or community art to propose ways of collaboratively visualising neighbourhood heat stories and data. The emphasis was placed on co-creation with residents, imaginative interpretation of citizen science data, and the ability to engage diverse publics through an eventual exhibition or presentation at Bibliotheek Neude. A fixed commission fee of €2,500 and a clear timeline for workshops (spring 2026) and exhibition (summer 2026) were set to provide clarity and feasibility, while leaving artistic approaches intentionally open-ended

Figure 9 Utrecht Pop-Up Lab initial call for submissions and 1 week countdown

The call was promoted through Urban ReLeaf networks, local cultural and environmental organisations, and municipal communication channels, positioning the Pop-Up Lab as both a creative commission and a civic engagement opportunity. The framing explicitly connected artistic practice with local climate action, highlighting access to resident-collected data, facilitative support from project partners, and the potential for international visibility through Urban ReLeaf's European network. This positioning aimed to attract practitioners motivated not only by artistic production, but also by social relevance and collaborative working with communities.

By the application deadline of 14 December 2025, the Utrecht Pop-Up Lab has received 12 submissions, representing a range of disciplines and approaches. At this stage, the selection and interview process is scheduled for January 2026, no production activity had yet taken place; however, project partners noted that the number and diversity of applications suggested that the open, theme-led framing successfully communicated both the relevance of the climate issue and the value placed on creative autonomy. The receipt of 12 proposals marked the completion of the first phase of the Pop-Up Lab cycle, establishing a solid foundation for the subsequent selection, co-creation and production stages.

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5 Cross-City Synthesis and Insights

This section synthesises emerging insights from the six Pop-Up Labs implemented in Athens, Dundee, Utrecht, Cascais, Mannheim and Riga. Despite operating in diverse cultural, social and environmental contexts, early outcomes have revealed consistent patterns in how creative practice can meaningfully engage citizens with environmental data and contribute to the objectives of Urban ReLeaf.

5.1 Creativity as a Bridge Between Data and Lived Experience

The Pop-Up Labs have highlighted the capacity of creative practice to provide accessible entry points into scientific practice, citizen science approaches and citizen-generated environmental data. While digital dashboards, maps and technology and indicators can feel abstract or detached, artistic translations enabled residents to encounter environmental information through sensory, emotional and place-based experiences. Sculpture using colour, light movement or sound made GBI variations tangible; participatory poetry linked heat-stress data to recognisable locations. These approaches supported embodied interpretation and reduced the perceived distance between “data producers” and “data users”.

Whilst it is at an early stage, these preliminary insights suggest that creative practice can complement scientific communication by engaging affective and experiential forms of understanding that are often absent from conventional data dissemination, particularly in relation to complex or long-term environmental challenges.

5.2 Strengthening Social Connection and Community Ownership

The Pop-Up Labs created shared spaces for dialogue and reflection, internal to the Urban ReLeaf cities themselves as well as participants. Participants indicated that it was easier to discuss environmental issues when in the process of ‘making’ or ‘creating’ and starting from personal experience rather than technical framing. Workshops and public events attracted participants beyond typical engagement demographics, including children, elderly residents, and newcomers. Creative activities also supported trust-building: the presence of artists softened institutional boundaries, making city representatives more approachable. This may signal that citizen-generated data carries cultural as well as technical value, we will explore this further.

5.3 New Roles for artists in cities for participatory data ecosystems

The Pop-Up Labs demonstrated the need and value of city contacts who know the creative and cultural landscape, and could maximised the in-kind opportunity for artists. The artists acted as mediators and critical sounding boards within urban data ecosystems. Artists identified gaps in communication, leveraged citizen perceptions, and reframed environmental issues through cultural lenses. Their role extended beyond producing creative outputs to facilitating dialogue, revealing emotional dimensions around environmental perceptions and supporting communities to articulate alternative futures.

5.4 Challenges encountered

Several shared challenges emerged across the consortium. The relatively low commission fee was a barrier for some cities who had statutory artist fees, this limited the possible outputs and use of official city platforms to advertise the opportunity. Short timescales limited the depth of participation in some contexts, particularly where longer-term permissions or relationship-building with communities was required. Some datasets proved too technical to explain easily, highlighting the need for more accessible or creative summaries for meaning-making or visual explanations. Logistical constraints, including permissions, procurement processes, weather conditions and availability of public space, sometimes restricted the scale or timing of activities. Ensuring equitable participation required sustained attention, particularly in relation to accessibility, translation and inclusive scheduling. These challenges provide important design considerations for future iterations and scaling of similar approaches.

5.5 Value for Municipal Processes and Future Governance

The Pop-Up Labs offered valuable insight into how creatively mediated data engagement can support municipal objectives, including increasing visibility of environmental issues, broadening participation and enabling new narratives around urban greening and climate resilience. Insights from the Labs inform Task 2.4 and will contribute to the participatory governance tools developed in WP5, particularly those addressing community engagement pathways, data literacy and co-creation methodologies.

5.6 Recommendations for replication

Drawing on cross-city insights from the Pop-Up Labs, the following recommendations are proposed for municipalities, Horizon Europe projects and cultural organisations seeking to replicate or adapt creative commissioning approaches for environmental engagement.

Design and Planning

1. If a deeper engagement is desired, embed creative practice early in participatory processes. Involve artists from the framing stage to explore questions, data gaps and community narratives, rather than limiting creative input to final engagement stages or for communication and dissemination.
2. Co-design briefs with city teams, this helps to ensure creative outputs respond to community priorities while aligning with municipal strategies.
3. Provide accessible data summaries and visual aids, prepare clear, non-technical representations of citizen-generated data to support meaningful engagement by artists and participants.

Commissioning and Support Structures

4. The use of small, flexible micro-commissions can foster experimentation, micro-commissions (typically in the range of €2,000–€5,000) can activate community spaces and enable responsive, low-risk experimentation.

5. Ensure transparent and inclusive selection processes, clear criteria, informal panels and open communication enhance trust, accountability and access.
6. Mentoring or in-kind support for data interpretation and participatory practice may be required. Artists can be paired with municipal staff and technical partners.

Engagement and Implementation

7. Prioritise accessible and welcoming public formats, select locations, formats and timings that support and widen participation. Consider target age groups, cultural backgrounds and abilities.
8. Combine creative outputs with participatory moments that invite active involvement rather than passive viewing.
9. Document processes as well as outputs, capture learning through reflections, visual documentation and process notes to support knowledge transfer.

Integration into governance

10. Creative commissions can link to municipal planning cycles, creative outputs could support consultation processes, climate adaptation planning and place-making initiatives however care is required regarding transparency.
11. Adopt creative commissioning frameworks as part of long-term participation strategies.
12. Feed insights into governance toolkits and policy guidance.

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6 Conclusion

This deliverable documents the design, implementation framework and application of the Community and Culture Pop-Up Labs developed under Task 2.3 of the Urban ReLeaf project. It presents the conceptual foundations underpinning the Pop-Up Lab approach, the five-phase methodology and associated tools developed to support cities, and an overview of early implementation across the six pilot cities. Together, these elements establish a coherent and transferable framework for embedding creative and cultural practice within citizen-powered environmental data ecosystems.

Through the Pop-Up Labs, Urban ReLeaf has operationalised a structured yet adaptable creative commissioning model that enables municipalities to work with artists and communities to interpret citizen-generated environmental data in publicly accessible ways. The methodology supports inclusive engagement, transparent commissioning, and ethical delivery, while remaining responsive to local governance contexts, community rhythms and practical constraints. The interim implementation documented in this deliverable demonstrates that the framework can be applied across diverse urban settings, institutional capacities and environmental themes.

As this is an interim deliverable, the Pop-Up Labs are at different stages of implementation across the pilot cities. The purpose of this report is therefore not to provide a final evaluation or comparative assessment of outcomes, but to consolidate methodological learning, document early experiences, and establish a shared evidence base for cross-city reflection. The insights presented here highlight both the potential of creative practice to support environmental data engagement and the practical considerations required to deliver such approaches within real-world municipal contexts.

A full synthesis of outcomes, drawing on completed city implementations, evaluation data and collective reflection, will be delivered through Task 2.4 Insights Workshops. The tested Pop-Up Lab methodology and creative commissioning framework documented in this deliverable will subsequently inform WP5's Urban ReLeaf Toolkit, contributing to wider guidance on inclusive, data-driven urban governance and participatory approaches to urban greening and climate adaptation. In this way, the work presented here provides a foundation for both continued project delivery and longer-term replication beyond the Urban ReLeaf consortium.

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Appendix 1

Precedent projects analysis informing Pop-Up Labs operations and methodology

Project	Focus & Scale	Key Creative Approach	Operational Lessons	Application to Urban ReLeaf
<p>Making Sense (2015-2018, Grant 688620)</p> <p>Coordinated by Waag Society, UD partner</p>	<p>Environmental sensing of air quality, noise and gamma radiation via nine citizen-sensing pilots in Amsterdam, Barcelona, Prishtina using Smart Citizen platform.</p>	<p>Sound walks, data sonification, participatory mapping, local festivals and maker/hacker 'commissions' with community engagement;</p> <p>Toolkit led by UD and partners Waag, IAAC, etc. (Citizen Sensing Toolkit) incl fablab facilitated artist outputs</p> <p>Citizens became community champions</p>	<p>Iterative co-design workshops aligned community concerns with sensing campaigns</p> <p>Creative activities surfaced experiential/affective dimensions missing in raw sensor data</p> <p>Creative translation built trust with initially sceptical residents</p> <p>In-kind support and expertise from partners was critical in the delivery and success of creative outputs.</p> <p>Creative outputs, case studies and interviews packaged into a reusable toolkit for replication - Citizen Sensing: A Toolkit</p> <p>Celebration using culture and creativity at the end of campaigns</p>	<p>Use creative modalities (festivals, sound walks, mapping, data-stories) to communicate urban environmental data and build trust with communities and local authorities</p> <p>Ensure roles and expectations for including in-kind support and expertise is clarified for cities and commissions</p> <p>Create templates and resources for Urban ReLeaf creative commissions and design.</p>
<p>GROW Observatory (2016-2019, Grant 690199)</p> <p>Led by UD</p>	<p>Citizen Science Soil monitoring & regenerative food-growing; >20,000 participants across Europe in 24 "GROW Places" in 13 countries using 6,500+ low-cost soil moisture sensors linked to</p>	<p>Co-created citizen-science experiments and visualisations; artistic commissions through open call process: <i>By the Code of Soil</i> (Kasia Molga + Scanner) transforming soil</p>	<p>Participatory design and creative outputs helped sustain engagement beyond initial sensor deployment</p> <p>Artists required accessible data formats and technical support to work</p>	<p>Adopt a co-design-first approach with Impact / Feasibility Matrix for Urban ReLeaf</p> <p>Position creative practice as knowledge-making, not just communication</p>

	Sentinel-1 EO validation.	sensor + Sentinel-1 data into an audio-visual artwork. (Molga studio / FutureEverything page)	<p>credibly with EO/sensor data</p> <p>Significant commission award (>7K) required specialist Creative Production knowledge to both realise and engage audiences with the final artwork.</p> <p>Artist reputation and work secured prestige venues e.g. Royal Academy, London, Centre Pompidou, Paris, for wide dissemination.</p> <p>Art made “invisible” soil/climate systems tangible for communities and decision-makers.</p>	<p>Leverage the GROW art-science model to embed creative / data commissions in Urban ReLeaf.</p> <p>Direct knowledge transfer via UD leadership</p> <p>Expertise in commissioning / art required on the panel.</p> <p>Important criteria such as quality of proposal, ambition and feasibility important. Evidence of high quality prior work / artistic reputation.</p>
<p>Dandelion UNBOXED: Creativity in the UK (2022)</p> <p>Dundee ‘Unexpected Garden’ co-led by UD</p>	<p>National “grow-your-own” STEAM programme across Scotland; festivals in Glasgow & Inverness; ~1,040 smaller events in 27/32 local authorities; 12–13 co-designed “Unexpected Gardens” with creative commissions</p> <p>Harvest reaching vulnerable communities through events in one season.</p>	<p>Place-based “Unexpected Gardens” in priority neighbourhoods co-designed with communities;</p> <p>Dundee creative commissions, using an open call process, embedded such as musicians-in-residence (St Kilda Mailboat), creative writing/planter illustration, mural (Zofia Chamienia) installation (Luke Jerram) ‘<i>Of Earth and Sky</i>’.</p>	<p>Modest micro-grants (e.g. community-led events) empowered local creative/data outcomes</p> <p>Emerging Creative Producers paired established orgs with local/emerging talent</p> <p>Embedding gardens in existing community spaces/festivals and planning for legacy increased trust/engagement especially among vulnerable communities</p> <p>Combining hands-on growing, citizen-science experiments and creative storytelling strengthened public engagement with food, climate and land-use issues.</p>	<p>Introduce micro-grant schemes (£1,500 - £7,000) to seed community-led creative/data projects</p> <p>Partner with local cultural organisations to communicate or host Urban ReLeaf activities within existing festivals, and networks.</p> <p>Design for legacy spaces that persist beyond funding</p> <p>Combine quantitative urban environmental with place-based creative narratives to support community advocacy and municipal dialogue.</p>

Appendix 2

Pop-Up Community and Culture Labs process and timeline

Quick Guide for City Pilots

Purpose

Commission an artist(s) to creatively activate existing citizen science data on city pilot topic e.g. heat spots and stress, thermal comfort, and greenspace perceptions into a highly accessible public-facing output e.g. artwork, lab or event.

Call for creative proposals, criteria, outputs

See related document ‘Call for creative proposals’, *Outputs matrix and Exemplars*

Timeline overview

Indicative Budget Template (€2.5k)

Item	Proportion	Amount	Example activity
Artist Fee	40%	€1,000	Commission (5 x days at €200 day rate)
Materials	40%	€1,000	Specific to the proposal and activities
Engagement	20%	€500	Artist engagement e.g. workshop with community groups and city stakeholders, refreshments etc
Evaluation	Additional	tbc	Supported by UNIVDUN - travel budget per city
Design	Additional	tbc	Supported by UNIVDUN design, graphics, evaluation and documentation
City Support	Optional	tbc	Additional discretionary budget increase / in-kind support through events, public engagement e.g. city events and festivals, use of public or community spaces.

Discussion topics that align to criteria

- **Budgetary constraints** - €2,500 budget - to include related costs (materials, permissions, facilitation).
- **Community engagement and facilitation** - outputs should support inclusivity, being particularly mindful of underrepresented groups.
- **Technical and skill feasibility** - the skills and expertise required to deliver each output (e.g., evidence of past projects)
- **Sustainability** - potential for long-term impact or legacy of the output, including maintenance if relevant, and future development.

Additional points

- **Discretionary budget increase** - City Pilots may wish to supplement the budget and commission a more ambitious output. In-kind support can also be offered e.g. use of equipment, spaces, materials and a beneficial association with an existing funded event or project.
- **Commission communications and submission process** – using existing city channels, platforms, and / or by email

Appendix 3

Urban ReLeaf Pop-Up Community and Culture Labs

Commission Outputs Matrix

An indicative range of artistic outputs that the Pop-Up Lab / commission / residency might produce. With key implications (logistical, technical, and community-related) that should be considered for each type of output.

Steps for Use

Use the matrix to consider the most viable options based on feasibility, budget, and alignment with city pilot aims.

Create a prioritised list of outputs in order to give examples in the commissioning brief.

- The creative outputs were identified during workshops, aligning with the pilot goals, communities, and resources.
-
- Consider implications such as community impact, logistical requirements, and technical considerations.
- Consider community and city assets e.g. spaces, local events, festivals, stakeholders and resources available.

Potential output	Description	Key Implications	Community Impact	Technical / Production Notes
Installation	Physical, site-specific work (e.g., sculpture, interactive art).	Permissions, location availability, materials sourcing, maintenance, weather resistance.	Highly visible; draws attention to urban greening initiatives.	Installation complexity, budget for construction, long-term maintenance.
Data visualisation	Artistic interpretation of citizen-generated or sensor data (e.g., graphs, AR). Single contribution.	Accurate data representation, user accessibility, integration with platforms like AR or digital screens.	Highlights data insights; engages data-driven audiences.	Software/tools expertise, budget for tech, digital platform compatibility.
Data crafts e.g. textiles	Data led printed textile, quilt, knit	Learning skills, identifying craft	Bespoke textile output, time to	Expertise in knit, print or other

	project or other textile project. Participatory or single contribution.	skills that community can learn, x generational, requires tools or equipment	create, requires engaging facilitation	textile, materials, location for 'classes'
Community mural	A painted or chalk mural or designed graffiti in a (permitted location).	Identifying a visible and accessible wall, permissions, supplies, co-creation workshops.	Strong community ownership; celebrates local identity.	Weatherproofing, maintenance, permissions for public spaces.
Performance incl poem, music, art	Live or recorded performance inspired by citizen gathered data.	Scheduling performances, venue selection, capturing audience attention, rehearsals.	Engages audiences in storytelling and brings data to life emotionally.	Venue logistics, audience accessibility, recording for legacy.
Storytelling project	Written, Audio, or visual storytelling (e.g. podcasts, short films). Participatory	Finding contributors, editing/publishing tools, distribution channels.	Builds personal connection to data and greening efforts.	Distribution format, content creation timeline, platform selection.
Creative Interactive workshop	A single or series of public events inviting community participation.	Scheduling, facilitator availability, securing workshop space, material preparation.	Directly engages community; fosters co-creation.	Timing, recruitment of participants, materials cost.
Temporary exhibition	Curated series of workshops and display of data led creative outputs.	Securing a temporary space, installation design, visitor flow, promotion.	Engages a wider public with project outcomes.	Space rental costs, exhibition design expertise, visitor management.
Digital artwork	Interactive, web-based art or app showcasing community/envir onmental data.	Tech development, platform hosting, user interface design.	Reaches broader audiences; easy to share online.	High technical expertise, ongoing hosting costs, cross-platform testing.
Community zine	Small-scale printed publication co-designed with residents.	Printing costs, co-creation workshops, distribution plan.	Creates a tangible legacy for the project; builds community pride.	Printing logistics, participant engagement for content creation.
Community food sharing and dialogue Project	Place based food-sharing initiative e.g., 'the place is the menu' inspired by place, people and culture.	Finding a suitable venue, working with local chefs or food specialists, menu creation, and event promotion.	Supports cultural exchange; celebrates local identity and traditions.	Venue logistics, catering partnerships, ensuring accessibility and inclusivity.
Visual glossary	A creative glossary of	Gathering input from diverse	Increases understanding of	Design and printing costs,

	highly local terms, dialects or concepts related to the project (e.g., citizen science, greening).	community voices, graphic design expertise.	complex ideas; builds shared language.	digital distribution, community input sessions.
Visual Map project	Artistic or participatory re-mapping of data and space, showing community assets or green areas.	Collaboration with local residents, data visualisation tools, permissions for map use.	Highlights local resources; deepens community connection to place.	Mapping software, permissions for public display, co-creation workshops.
Community Podcast Series	Multi-episode audio series featuring resident voices, local sounds, and data sonification	Equipment access, editing skills, ongoing content creation	Builds storytelling capacity; preserves community voices	Recording equipment, hosting platform, distribution strategy
VR/AR Walking Trails	Virtual or augmented reality experiences triggered at specific locations using community data	Technical complexity, smartphone accessibility, location permissions, VR headset availability	Transforms everyday spaces; encourages exploration; accessible to mobility-restricted residents	AR/VR development expertise, GPS accuracy, device compatibility, headset loan system
Community Board Game	Custom board game based on local data, geography, or community challenges	Game design expertise, play-testing, production costs	Builds social connections; educational tool for ongoing use	Design iteration, printing/manufacturing, rules clarity
Sensory Garden Installation	Data-responsive garden elements (lighting, sound, scent) reflecting community metrics	Horticultural knowledge, sensor integration, maintenance requirements	Creates contemplative space; demonstrates data through nature	Weather-resistant technology, plant selection, ongoing care protocols
Community Time Capsule Project	Digital and physical archive of current community state, to be opened in future	Long-term storage, community input gathering, future access planning	Builds intergenerational connection; documents change over time	Archive format standards, physical storage security, digital preservation
Micro-Residency Network	Series of very short (1-3 day) artist residencies in community spaces	Artist selection, space identification, community hosting	Brings external perspectives; builds cultural confidence	Artist logistics, insurance, space preparation

Community Radio Station	Temporary or permanent hyperlocal radio broadcasting community stories and data	Broadcasting licenses, equipment setup, presenter training	Amplifies resident voices; creates ongoing dialogue platform	Radio equipment, licensing requirements, content programming
Geocaching Data Trail	GPS treasure hunt using environmental data as clues and waypoints	Location permissions, weatherproof containers, smartphone access	Gamifies environmental awareness; encourages physical exploration	GPS accuracy, container maintenance, riddle/puzzle design
Community Memory Palace	Digital archive combined with physical memory triggers throughout neighborhood	Digital archiving, community storytelling sessions, location mapping	Preserves intangential knowledge; creates living heritage	Web development, oral history recording, location-based triggers
Biomimicry Design Lab	Workshops creating solutions inspired by local nature and environmental data	Scientific expertise, materials for prototyping, space for experimentation	Develops environmental observation skills; fosters innovation thinking	Workshop materials, expert facilitators, documentation systems
BioBlitz	identification event where community identifies local species/environmental features, poetry slam style with expert mentors	Expert naturalist availability, identification resources, weather contingency, equipment for documentation	Builds environmental literacy; creates excitement around local biodiversity; generates citizen science data	Field guides, magnifying glasses, cameras, weather protection, data recording systems

Appendix 4

Urban ReLeaf Pop-Up Community and Culture Labs

Submissions, Reviewing, Shortlisting and Interview process

Submissions handling

1. Setup

In your WP2 > T2.3 > City folder:

- Create a submissions folder and upload all received applications.
- Create a copy of the submission spreadsheet

2. Logging Submissions

- Log each submission on the submission spreadsheet.
- Check the submissions (CV, budget, two-page application, etc.), and mark off required submissions as complete or incomplete on the checklist

Reviewing and Shortlisting

3. Reviewing

- Nominate the reviewers – include Staff Member (representing UoD), City team member (Name) nominate a third UR team member from the City or another team.
- Share the submissions folder with all reviewers.

4. Shortlisting

- Agree interview date with the review panel – Notify shortlisted applicants and include information about the panel members, interview procedure incl presentation.
- Shortlist applicants with complete applications i.e. incl CV, Budget etc
- Use the scoring and criteria - outlined below (also provided in the guidelines).
- Compile reviewers' scores
- Invite 3–4 applicants with highest scores to interview

Reviewing and Criteria

Each **complete** application will be scored against the criteria using the following 0–2 scale

- 0 = Not evidenced
- 1 = Some evidence, but limited
- 2 = Good evidence

Criteria (see guidelines):

- Community engagement approach
- Communication, quality, and creativity of proposal
- Budget feasibility and delivery plan

- Track record, evidence of skills, and prior projects

5. Interview Procedure

- Maximum length: 20 – 30 minutes per applicant – same for all
- Format: 7–10 minute presentation by the artist on their previous projects and their application
- Panel questions.
- The same questions should be asked of each artist to ensure fairness, based on the criteria.

Panel Interview and Schedule (20-30mins)

Introductions to the panel members

Warm-up question (or similar) - Can you give an example of relevant past project where you have overcome an issue, how did you navigate and resolve this for successful delivery.

Criteria Questions

Q1 Community Engagement:

- Do you plan to involve the local community in this project, what support do you need?
- How would you ensure inclusivity and accessibility, what support do you need?

Q2 Proposal Quality & Creativity

- How does your proposal align with the aims of this commission, how can we help?

Q3 Budget & Delivery

- What challenges to delivery do you anticipate and how will you manage them?

Q4 Track Record

- Can you give an example of a past project where you have used similar skills?
- What makes you confident you can deliver this commission successfully?

After the presentation and questions, the panel should re-grade each applicant against the criteria.

Panel agrees on the successful artist according to scores and discussion.

6. Final Steps

- Confirm the support required for delivery, and conditions of the award to the selected artist.
- Confirm the start date, and document the final completion date.
- Pass the awardee details to Dundee.

Please ensure each stage is recorded. Including all scoring and notes for reporting and uploaded to your WP2 > T2.3 > City folder

Appendix 5

Pop-Up Community and Culture Labs

Call for Creative Proposals sample text

City of [Insert City Name]

About the Opportunity

We invite artists, creative practitioners, designers, and community facilitators to apply for a Euro 2,500 commission to bring urban climate stories and data to life. Through this commission, you will work closely with community members to make data and stories collected by local residents visible, meaningful, and engaging for the wider community. We want to create creative experiences that spark conversation, elevate community voices, and inspire action.

Why This Matters

Climate change affects us all, but not everyone experiences it equally. Some neighbourhoods have less green space, hotter streets, or poorer air quality. The data collected by local residents tells real stories about how people experience their city every day.

What's Urban ReLeaf?

This is part of the Urban ReLeaf project, which helps cities become greener, healthier, and more connected by involving residents in collecting environmental data about their local urban spaces.

Citizens have gathered data on:

- **Urban heat and thermal comfort**
- **Green spaces, how we use them and how accessible they are**
- **Air quality, biodiversity, and trees**
- **How public spaces feel to people who live, work, and play there**

Now we want to work with a creative practitioner to turn this data into something the whole city can experience, enjoy, and reflect on.

You don't need to be a scientist. We're looking for creativity, curiosity, and an interest in working with people and places.

What support will be available (to be developed bespoke to each city)

- You'll work closely with the Urban ReLeaf team, including community organisations, city partners, and researchers.
- We will support community engagement activities, help you access the data, and can offer facilitation or mentoring where needed.
- We'll support the final showcase and promotion through Urban ReLeaf's local and European networks

What we're looking for (to be developed bespoke to each city)

We welcome creative ideas including (but not limited to):

- Public art installations, murals, or temporary artworks
- Performances, poetry, sound works, and events
- Participatory workshops or co-created projects and hands-on activities
- Storytelling, zines, data visualisation, or digital experiences

Who can apply?

You do not need prior experience working with scientific or environmental data.

- Artists, designers, performers, facilitators, and creative collectives
- People with experience of community co-creation or participatory practice
- Practitioners interested in environmental, social, or justice issues
- Creatives at any stage of career, including those from underrepresented or marginalised backgrounds

The commission

- **Budget:** £2,500 (this includes your fee, materials, travel, production and any expenses).
- **Delivery period:** over approx. 3–4 months, starting from [Insert Date].
- **Location:** [Insert City Name]

How we'll select

Proposals will be assessed in two phases,

Phase 1 Submission of your short proposal and paperwork

Phase 2 Short interview (online) for shortlisted submissions

Criteria	Proportion
Community engagement approach	35%
Communication, quality & creativity of proposal	25%
Budget feasibility & delivery plan	20%
Track record e.g. evidence of skills and prior projects	20%

Key Dates (tbc)

Call Opens | [Insert Date]
Submission Deadline | [Insert Date]
Interviews | [Insert Date]
Commission Awarded | [Insert Date]
Community Engagement Begins | [Insert Date]
Delivery & Activation | [Insert Date]
Evaluation & Wrap-up | [Insert Date]

How to apply

Please submit your proposal and documents to: [Insert Contact Email]
If you have questions or access needs, contact [Insert Contact Name & Info]. We're happy to discuss adjustments or support to make applying accessible for you.

What we need from you:

A short proposal (max 2 pages) including:

- Your idea and how you'll approach it
- How you'll involve the community
- What kind of creative outputs you're imagining
- Any thoughts on legacy or longer-term impact

Plus:

2. A simple budget breakdown.
3. A rough timeline.
4. Up to 5 examples of relevant work.
5. A short biography or CV.
6. 2 references

Additional Notes

- Urban ReLeaf values inclusion and sustainability.
- We encourage low-carbon, ethical production.
- We will help connect you with local groups and provide guidance on working with community data.
- Successful projects may be showcased across Urban ReLeaf's European network.

Your proposal should ideally:

- Involve and include local people who contributed to the data
- Spark curiosity and connection
- Be accessible and engaging for broad audiences
- Reflect a commitment to climate justice, inclusion, and environmental responsibility
- Consider sustainable and ethical production approaches